

Role of Platelet Indices in Diagnosing Acute Appendicitis at a Tertiary Care Center: Correlation with The Alvarado Scoring SystemSadiya Mirji¹, Pratibha Patil², Shashikala H Madiwalar³, Tejaswini Vallabha⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Al Ameen Medical College and Hospital, Vijayapura, Karnataka²Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Al Ameen Medical College and Hospital, Vijayapura, Karnataka³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, Koppal Institute of Medical Sciences, Koppal, Karnataka⁴Professor, Department of General Surgery, BLDE (Deemed to be University) Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka

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Abstract:**Aim:** Clinically misdiagnosed acute appendicitis still continues to be a cause of negative appendectomy. This study emphasizes on utilising platelet indices as aid in parameter for the clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis using the Alvarado scoring system.**Materials and Methods:** The blood samples of patients, who were clinically diagnosed as acute appendicitis on the basis of the Alvarado scoring system and healthy controls attending the routine check-up clinic were collected in di potassium(k₂)-Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) vacutainers and were processed by Sysmex XN1000 haematology analyser.**Results:** The study group comprised of 102 patients clinically diagnosed as acute appendicitis using the Alvarado scoring system, out of which 84 cases histopathologically confirmed as acute appendicitis. PDW and P-LCR were found to have higher statistically significant values in the patients compared to the age and sex matched 84 healthy controls (11.5± 2.2fl vs 10.6±1.3fl and 24.8± 6.6% vs 22.0± 5.2%). On Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis the sensitivity and specificity of PDW were found to be 60% and 73% respectively and for P-LCR, sensitivity was 58% and specificity was 56%.**Conclusion:** In the present study it is emphasized that platelet indices like PDW and P-LCR can be used as supportive aid for the clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis and utility of these parameters as one of the clinical components of the Alvarado scoring system.**Keywords:** Acute appendicitis, Alvarado score, Platelet indices, Platelet distribution widthThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Acute appendicitis (AA) is one of the commonest causes of emergency abdominal surgeries. The diagnosis is done mainly on the basis of clinical presentation. However, the etiology of appendicitis is not clear, it is considered to be multifactorial. A patient presenting as simple appendicitis may end up in developing perforation of the appendix, that may lead to much higher morbidity and mortality, the surgeon is solely to decide whether to operate the case on the probable diagnosis or wait until it is certain. [1,2]

The surgical principle about acute appendicitis which states "when in doubt, take it out", is not correct as such the procedure often comes out with accompanied few complications. Though AA is a common problem, its diagnosis continues to be a challenge for physicians. A confirmed diagnosis is possible at the surgery and after histopathological

examination of an appendectomy specimen. Hence, it is quite difficult to get a preoperative definitive diagnosis. According to the world literature the rate of negative appendectomy is about 20-40%, the associated morbidity rate with it is about 10%. [3,4]

The probable clinical diagnosis of AA can be done by various scoring systems, among all scoring systems the most commonly followed scoring system is the Alvarado scoring system, based on the clinical history, physical examination, and few hematological parameters like total leucocyte count, shift to left. This system is simple to apply and to calculate the score accordingly.[5] Although imaging technologies such as ultrasonography (USG), computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are promising but they are not adequate. The main disadvantage of these investigations is that they are costly, and these are

more helpful in the emergency conditions rather than routine.[6]

Emergency rooms routinely use the complete blood cell count (CBC) parameters, which also displays platelets indices. PIs serve as markers for platelet activation. Larger platelets are more active than smaller ones, and there is a correlation between platelet size and activity and function. As a result, MPV may be utilized as a biomarker in conditions like massive hemorrhage, leukemia, vasculitis, diabetes mellitus, inflammatory disorders, sepsis-like conditions, myeloproliferative diseases, and post-splenectomy conditions. Variability in platelet size, which may indicate active platelet release, is indicated by PDW. Research has shown that under a number of circumstances, PDW is also different from MPV when compared to healthy subjects.[7]

Thus, in the developing countries the search for easily accessible and cost-effective biomarker is the need of the hour for the more accurate clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis. Besides substantial morbidity and mortality, negative appendectomy is also liable for the loss of valuable time of medical staff and economical resources. Platelet indices are easy to record and can be done routinely along with the complete blood count using an automated analyzer. So, we undertook this study to evaluate the utility of platelet indices in the clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis.

Materials and Methods

After approval by the Institutional Ethical Committee, a prospective hospital-based study was carried out from December 2017 to June 2019 at Shri B.M. Patil Medical College, Hospital and Research centre, Vijayapura. 102 patients of clinically diagnosed as acute appendicitis using the Alvarado scoring system, were chosen based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Histopathologically confirmed 84 patients of acute appendicitis platelet

indices were compared with age and sex matched 84 healthy controls.

Method of Data Collection

All subject's clinical history was taken as per the study proforma and then complete clinical examination was carried out. The blood samples of the patients were drawn from the antecubital vein using a 5ml syringe and immediately mixed in k2-EDTA vacutainers. The sample was processed within 2-hours of venepuncture using the 6-part automated Hematology analyzer (Sysmex XN-1000) and complete blood count analysis of the sample was done along with the platelet indices (MPV, PDW, PCT and P-LCR). The patients who underwent appendectomy in the Department of General Surgery of the institute. The appendectomy specimen of such patients was sent to the Histopathology section of the Department of Pathology for histopathological examination.

Inclusion criteria were, clinically diagnosed patients of acute appendicitis using the Alvarado scoring system, age and sex matched healthy controls attending routine clinical check-up. Exclusion criteria were subjects on antiplatelet drugs such as aspirin and clopidogrel, subjects with thrombocytopenic conditions such as dengue, malaria, and subjects with any diagnosed malignancy. Only the patients with histopathological reported as acute appendicitis were included for the calculation of platelet indices

For assessment of results, the patients were categorized into two groups, patients with score >7 were considered as positive i.e., patients with clinically high predictivity of acute appendicitis and ≤7 negative i.e., patients who had an equivocal probability of acute appendicitis. (Table 1)

Table 1: Distribution of patients by the Alvarado score and histopathology report

Alvarado score	Histopathology report		Total
	Acute appendicitis	Chronic appendicitis	
Positive (Score >7)	66	9	75
Negative (Score ≤7)	18	9	27
Total	84	18	102

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were recorded in Microsoft Excel sheet and the data were analyzed using SPSS software v.23.0. and. Numbers and percentage values were used to display descriptive qualitative data, whereas descriptive quantitative data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Chi square tests were used to compare categorical variables such as the Alvarado score and histopathologically confirmed

cases of acute appendicitis. Using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis, the diagnostic value and cut-off points of laboratory parameters that indicate the presence of acute appendicitis were determined. The p-value <0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 102 patients clinically diagnosed as acute appendicitis using the Alvarado scoring system were chosen, out of which 84 cases were

histopathologically confirmed as acute appendicitis. The results were analyzed only for histopathologically confirmed acute appendicitis cases. These patients' platelet indices parameters such as MPV, PDW, PCT and P-LCR were compared with the age and sex matched 84 healthy controls.

Our study showed sensitivity 93.33%, specificity 80%, positive predictive value 88%, and negative predictive value 84.21% for the Alvarado scoring system for the patients with clinically diagnosed as acute appendicitis.

Majority of the patients diagnosed with acute appendicitis were in the 2nd to 3rd decades of their life. The male to female ratio was 3.1:1. The total number of males diagnosed with acute appendicitis among cases were 57 (67.9%) and females cases were 27 (32.1%).

The mean values of hematological parameters of patients were evaluated and compared with the control group. These parameters included TLC,

Neutrophil percentage(N%), Lymphocyte percentage(L%), Platelet count (PLT).

The various hematological parameters' mean values were, the TLC 12609.3±4062.8/cmm in patients and 8147.3±1662.1/cmm in controls (p value <0.001), the N% was 77.5±13.1% and L% was 17.6±11.8% in acute appendicitis cases. Total leucocyte count and the neutrophil percentage were significantly higher in acute appendicitis patients. The mean value of PLT was 2.7±0.8lakhs/ μ l (p value 0.864).

The platelet indices of 84 patients were evaluated and compared with platelet indices of age and sex-matched 84 healthy controls. The mean MPV in acute appendicitis patients was 9.7± 1.2fl with pvalue 0.914 and the mean PDW was 11.5± 2.2fl in acute appendicitis group compared to the healthy controls where it was 10.6±1.3fl. We observed that the mean value of PDW and P-LCR were significantly higher in acute appendicitis patients in comparison to healthy controls. (**Table 2**)

Table 2: Distribution of mean of various hematological parameters between the cases and controls.

Parameters	Patients (n=84)		Healthy controls (n=84)		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
TLC (cells/cmm)	12609.3	4062.8	8147.3	1662.1	<0.001*
N%	77.5	13.1	60.7	7.2	<0.001*
L%	17.6	11.8	31.5	7.0	<0.001*
PLT (lakhs/cmm)	2.7	0.8	2.7	0.6	0.864
MPV (fl)	9.7	1.2	9.6	0.7	0.914
PDW (fl)	11.5	2.2	10.6	1.3	0.002*
PCT (%)	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.81
P-LCR (%)	24.8	6.6	22.0	5.2	0.003*

Note: * significant at 5% level of significance (p<0.05)

The study group's mean PI parameters were compared with the Alvarado score but except for PCT value, no other parameter showed significant

variation, which was 0.3±0.1% in the patients which had score ≥ 7 as compared to 0.2±0.1% in patients with score <7 (p value 0.044). (**Table 3**)

Table 3: Mean of platelet indices distribution according to the Alvarado score

Platelet indices	Alvarado score <7		Alvarado score ≥ 7		p value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
MPV (fl)	10.1	1.0	10.0	1.1	0.661
PDW (fl)	11.7	1.9	11.4	2.3	0.593
PCT (%)	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.044*
P-LCR (%)	25.5	4.2	24.6	7.1	0.606

ROC curve analysis (**Figure 1**) was performed to get the best cutoff value, the area under the curve (AUC), sensitivity and specificity for all the parameters. The area under the curve for TLC was 0.854 and (N%) was 0.836. AUC for PDW and P-LCR was 0.617 and 0.623, respectively. TLC showed higher sensitivity and specificity of 77% and 75% respectively, at a cutoff of 9540cells/cmm.

Neutrophil percentage, lymphocyte percentage had a sensitivity and specificity of 73% and 71%; 71.4% and 72.6%; respectively. In platelet indices parameters, the PDW cutoff value for clinically predicting acute appendicitis was 10.7fl, which had a sensitivity of 60% and specificity of 58%, which was highest among all other platelet indices.

Figure 1: Receiver Operating Characteristic curve analysis of all parameters studied

Discussion

Although there are many advances with the invention of advanced investigations available in the diagnostic sector, the diagnosis of acute appendicitis continues to be a diagnostic dilemma for the clinician. Due to the variable presentation of acute appendicitis and a lack of reliable diagnostic tests, the clinical diagnosis remains unclear. The available investigations like USG and CT scan are expensive, time-consuming and need more advanced equipment and experience. [2,3] However, some investigations are not feasible and not available easily at point of care centers in developing nations.

The precision of clinical examination ranges from 71 to 97% and varies widely based on the examiner's experience. Since missing a perforated appendix has immediate and life-threatening complications, surgeons have generally accepted a 20% rate of negative appendectomy.[8] Thus, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the diagnostic utility of platelet indices and its association with the clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis, done by using the Alvarado scoring system to get a more accurate clinical diagnosis.

Leukocyte and neutrophil counts are the most commonly used laboratory parameters in medical practice for acute appendicitis diagnosis. Both parameters were significantly higher (p value <0.001) in acute appendicitis patients of present study,

which is similar to the literature. [4,5,7,9] We observed that leucocytosis a consistent finding in

majority of acute appendicitis cases along with neutrophilia and lymphocytopenia.

The various studies conducted on acute appendicitis and role of MPV in its diagnosis suggested that variation in the MPV values is acceptable, such as increased [10] or decreased levels [8] or no significant difference [9,11,12] as found in our study also. Although, in our study an increase in MPV was found but it was not statistically significant when compared with the healthy control group (p value 0.914) which was in concordance with studies conducted by Toktas O *et al* [9] Boshnaket *al*[11] and Ulukentet *al*[12], thus ruling out MPV association in predicting acute appendicitis. We got a cut off of 9.8fl (p value 0.005*) for which sensitivity was 57% and specificity was 55%.

Both MPV and PDW are platelet immaturity markers, and an increase in both as compared to controls indicates that young platelets are entering into the peripheral circulation.[13] Our evaluation showed that PDW was significantly increased, with p value= 0.002 in the patients of acute appendicitis (11.5±2.2 fl) as compared to the control group (10.6±1.3 fl). Similar results were noted in other studies done by Dincetal [7], Boshnaet *al*[11], Ulukentet *al*[12] and Mehmet *et al*[14]. Hence, it was evaluated that increased PDW can be used as a prognostic indicator of disease activity in acute appendicitis. In present study, we got a cut off of 10.7fl for PDW, for which sensitivity was 60% and specificity was 73%. This was comparable with the other studies mentioned in the table below. (Table 4) However, specificity was found to be less in our study.

Table 4: Comparison of platelet distribution width (pdw) in acute appendicitis with other studies

Publication	Country	Cases	PDW (fl)	Controls	PDW (fl)	p value
Dincet <i>al</i> [7]	Turkey	295	49.0(10.6-86.5)	100	18.4(10.3-62.5)	<0.001
Boshnak N <i>et al</i> [11]	Egypt	125	14.25±2.10	55	12.85±0.96	<0.001
Ulukentet <i>al</i> [12]	Turkey	97	15±2	94	13±2	<0.0001
Mehmet <i>et al</i> [14]	Turkey	455	19.01±1.68	114	16.77±1.81	<0.001
Present study	India	84	11.5±2.2	84	10.6±1.3	0.002

A study done by Mehmet *et al*[14]evaluated the role of platelet indices in acute appendicitis with correlation the Alvarado score however they have only mentioned PDW and its relationship with the Alvarado score. They found that PDW was not significant when it was compared with the Alvarado score. Our study also got similar results. Thus, it showed that there is no association between the Alvarado score and PDW. Also, our study results were in concordance with study done by Kostakis *et al*[15] for PCT value. Although the statistically significant change in PCT value may indicate the involvement of platelets in pathophysiology of acute appendicitis. However, its role in diagnosis of acute appendicitis is not clear yet.

The P-LCR parameter is generated by only a few analysers, with the Sysmex analyser being one of them. It is not often quoted in literature, probably because it is relatively a new Platelet Volume Indices (PVI) parameter. The value of P-LCR observed in our study in acute appendicitis group was 24.8±6.6% compared to healthy controls group where it was 22.0±5.2% (p value 0.0003). However, reverse to our study a study done by Madani *et al*[16]“Role of platelet parameters as a biomarker in diagnosis of acute appendicitis: A retrospective case-controlled study” evaluated P-LCR value, which in cases was 24.7% and 23.55% in controls group there was an increase in P-LCR values in their study but it was not statistically significant,

but in our study, we got a significantly higher P-LCR value (p value 0.0003) in acute appendicitis cases when compared with the healthy controls. Thus, we emphasize that further research is needed in this regard to confirm the variations in P-LCR values in acute appendicitis.

Limitations

Due to the small sample size and single-center design of the current study, participation from the other Indian regions is restricted. The current study's findings can be validated with the aid of additional multicenter research with bigger sample sizes.

Conclusion

The platelet indices play an important role in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis and can be used in predicting it preoperatively. Since there is no definitive and cost-effective method is available for the clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis, utilizing

these predictive parameters may be helpful in reducing the unnecessary surgery, complications, and mortality in high-risk cases. Out of the four platelet indices parameters (MPV, PDW, PCT and P-LCR), PDW showed increased values with highest sensitivity, followed by P-LCR. Thus, these parameters can aid in the clinical diagnosis of acute appendicitis and further can be added as a component of the Alvarado scoring system.

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